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Over - Valuation of IPO: A Red Alert for Investors

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Abstract: With more access to the Capital Market each and every company now is preferring the route of IPOs for raising the capital. However, there are many aspects that need to be looked down while going or applying for the IPO both from the company and investor point of view. This article initially focuses on the different motivating factors for the company to come up with their IPO. It also picturizes the factors that needed to be looked into while applying for the IPO and finally it focuses on the different reasons which ultimately leads to the Over Valuation of IPO. This article concludes that investor should exercise due diligence when they came across such over-valued IPO as in the long run the market price is much lower than the issue price and ultimately results into negative return for the investors.

Key Words: IPO Issue, Investors, Valuation, Alert, Risk

Introduction

Before going public, a business is considered private. Being a privately held firm, the company has grown with a very limited number of shareholders, including professional investors like venture capitalists or angel investors as well as early investors like the founders' family, friends, and colleagues. A company will start promoting its interest in going public when it reaches a point in its development where it believes it is developed enough and will now function towards rewards for public shareholders. Many investors who participate in IPOs are not aware of the process by which a company's value is determined.

An initial public offering (IPO) is the process by which a privately-owned enterprise is transformed into a public company whose shares are traded on a stock exchange. The process of IPO transforms a privately-held company into a public company. An IPO is generally initiated to infuse the new equity capital to the firm, to facilitate easy trading of the existing assets, to raise capital for the future or to monetize the investments made by existing stakeholders.

As an investor, it can be challenging to analyze a company with a stock that is newly issued and that has not been traded previously on an exchange. But smart investors can try to understand a company's financials by looking at its registration documents and assessing the company's financials in order to determine if the stock is priced appropriately. In addition, understanding the various components of how an investment bank conducts a company's IPO valuation is important for anyone interested in becoming an early investor.

Types of IPO

There are two common types of IPO. They are-

1) Fixed Price Offering

Under fixed price, the company going public determines a fixed price at which its shares are offered to investors. The investors know the share price before the company goes public. Demand from the markets is only known once the issue is closed. To partake in this IPO, the investor must pay the full share price when making the application.

The demand for the stocks in the market can be known once the issue is closed. If the investors partake in this IPO, they must ensure that they pay the full price of the shares when making the application. It is one of the popular methods which is generally being adopted by SME companies while bringing there IPO.

Eg: Shanthala FMCG Products Ltd

1) Appointing A Underwriter

- To kickstart the IPO process in India, companies need to approach market experts called underwriters or lead managers. They generally act as a intermediaries between companies and their investors.

2) Registering for IPO

- It includes creating a Draft Red Herring Prospectus (DRHP) and the registration statement. This is mandatory as per the Companies Act, and DRHP should consist of all compulsory disclosures as per the Companies Act and SEBI.

3) SEBI Approval

- After submitting a Red Herring Prospectus, The Stock Exchange Board reviews the application. The board ensures that every important detail about the company is available to its prospective investors

4) Applying for Listing

- The next step in the IPO process in India is applying for a listing on the stock exchange, where it plans to float the issue namely on the Bombay Stock Exchange or the National Stock Exchange.

5) Setting Up the Price of IPO

- Companies can now initiate the pricing of an IPO either through a fixed price IPO or a bookbinding offer.

6) Distribution of Shares

- Once the IPO price is decided, the company and its underwriter will analyse the shares allotted to each category of investor

This company's IPO opened for subscription on October 27, 2023 and closed on October 31, 2023. The face value of the company stock was ₹10 per share, and the IPO price was fixed at ₹91 per share.

2) Book Building Offering

In the case of book building, the company initiating an IPO offers a 20% price band on the stocks to the investors. Interested investors bid on the shares before the final price is decided. Here, the investors need to specify the number of shares they intend to buy and the amount they are willing to pay per share. In the book building issue, the price is released during the process of IPO. The lowest share price is referred to as floor price and the highest stock price is known as cap price. The ultimate decision regarding the price of the shares is determined by investors' bids. It is perhaps a realistic approach to pricing that is based on demand for the shares and not set by management and is being generally adopted by Main Board IPO Companies.

Eg: Zomato

This company's IPO opened for subscription on 14 July, 2021 and closed on 16 July, 2021. The face value of the company stock was Rs. 1 per share, and the IPO price band was Rs. 72 to Rs. 76.

Steps Involved in the IPO Process**Objectives of the Study:**

- 1) To Understand the reasons behind bringing the IPO.
- 2) To identify the components or factors involved in analyzing the IPO.
- 3) To understand the reasons for the over valuation of recent IPOs.

Different Underlying Reasons behind bringing the IPO

- 1) **Need of Working Capital:** To raise working capital for activities like expanding its current business into other verticals or growing its customer base by opening physical stores in untapped areas. In addition, the company could use the funds for research and developing new products.
- 2) **To Offload their existing debt burden:** Many companies are being heavy loaded with the amount of debt in their capital structure. So with the help of money raised through the route of IPO, they like to reduce their current debt burden.
- 3) **Liquidity for Company's Founders /Promoters:** Promoters generally hold the shares in the variety of private enterprises. If they wish to have more liquidity onto their hands then they generally adopt the route of offer for sale (OFS) in the IPO, thereby offering the shares to the public.
- 4) **Mergers and Acquisition:** A well-managed company is frequently a target for mergers or acquisitions by large corporations. Additionally, companies use IPO proceeds to fund mergers.

A successful IPO provides a company with value, reputation, status, and additional finances for funding any merger and acquisition deals.

- 5) **Creditability and Branding:** Through an IPO, a company's visibility and credibility may grow. Furthermore, with SEBI's strict regulation and periodic reporting procedures, the financial data is readily available to everyone. Thus, offering more transparency.
- 6) **Dual Tracking:** Dual tracking is a phenomenon where a company's IPO and sell-out occurs in sequence over a short period of time. For many companies, going public increases its valuation, brings credibility and accountability.
- 7) **Liquidity for Employees:** Many unlisted companies offer ESOPs (Employee Stock Option Plans) to its employees. Under these type ESOPs schemes, restricted share units (RSU) are offered to the employees for the long-term association with the company in future i.e. retention. Through IPO, company here would be providing an exit opportunity to the employees and hence creating liquidity in their hands.
- 8) **Boosts Market Presence**
Many a times investors are unaware of the company launching the IPO and hear about it for the first time during the launch period. As the company promotes and advertises its public offer, investors start researching the company, reading up on its business and financials, etc. This helps boost the market presence of the company. It can also use this buzz to grow its business.

To identify the components or factors involved in analyzing the IPO.

Being a investor, it becomes utmost important to know what are the different components or factors which should be analyzed during an IPO of a company and thus can make up a decision of whether to invest in the company or not.

- 1) **Overview of the Industry**
First and foremost, investor should have a basic understanding of the industry in which the company is operating. This includes reading up on the laws and regulations relevant to that industry. Future of the industry and the market share of the company in the industry should also be looked in.
- 2) **Look Up at the Draft Red Herring Prospectus:**
Investor should read thoroughly the draft red prospectus of the company which contains the details about the company's growth prospects, market vision, structuring, founders, reputation etc. By this investor will be able to get the idea about when, where and how much the raised capital would be used.
- 3) **Management Team:** Investor should also do a research and have a track record of the management team. This is important to gauge whether it is capable enough to stabilize its operations and the direction they are expected to take. It is important to understand how much interest the promoters or the management holds in the company before investing in an IPO.
- 4) **Diving Deep into the Company's Financials**
A company's financials are the most reliable data to determine whether you should proceed with the IPO or not. A good company have a sound financial performance as well as good future growth prospects. It should also have considerable cash reserves along with a low debt burden.
- 5) **Pricing of the IPO:** A price band is the range between the expected ceiling (maximum) and floor (minimum) prices within which the sale of the share will be expected to be conducted. The right price of a stock is usually determined by competitor analysis based on brand value, financial strategy etc. The company's brand value must be read in conjunction with its P/E (Price-to-Earnings) and P/S (Price-to-Sales) ratios , debt equity ratio, return on equity etc.to estimate the fair price of its stock through a competitor analysis. If these ratios are higher than those of its competitors, then the stock may be overpriced and thus avoidable.
- 6) **Deciding your risk tolerance level:** Before jumping into the making investment into any company's IPO it becomes important for investor to make a decision with respect to the risk appetite that he/she would be carrying. (low risk, moderate risk or high risk).

Reasons for the over valuation of recent IPOs.

Earlier we have seen that investor should look onto the different components for analyzing the IPO. However, many a times, questions on the pricing of the IPO arises. Sometimes the IPO issue of a certain company is underpriced and sometimes the IPO issue of a certain company is overpriced. In recent

times it has been evident that most of the IPOs of the company are being overpriced. Here are some of the reasons or factors behind the same:

- 1) To maximize their fund raising - Companies are always keen on getting more and more capital being injected into their business. As a result, when the company is first time coming in the Primary Market, some of them may have a view of putting the floor and ceiling price high so that it would get more capital from the investors and investors ultimately get trapped into the same.
- 2) Hype and Enthusiasm: Companies often generate hype and enthusiasm around their IPO to attract investor attention via different modes like advertising, media, finance influencer etc. The excitement and positive sentiment can result in investors being more willing to pay a premium for the company's shares, driving the valuation higher without really looking into the business of company or future prospects of the company.
- 3) Misleading or Unrealistic Information: Many a times misleading or unrealistic information is been shown in the prospectus that is being issued by the company which perhaps might attract the attention of the investors. It has been noticed that though it is duty of the investor to read the prospectus carefully before investing in the proposed company but majority of them lack in reading the same due to many reasons and the company takes undue advantage of the same. Moreover, with only three or four years' data shared in the red herring prospectus, it becomes difficult to assess how it will fare in less favourable parts of the business and economic cycle.
- 4) Underpricing Risk: Underwriters face the challenge of balancing the desire to maximize fundraising with the risk of underpricing the IPO. To mitigate the risk of leaving money on the table, they may set a higher initial valuation, which can contribute to overvaluation. It also creates fear in the minds of underwriters as if they price less there might a loss of their credibility and they might also not get future contracts.

Conclusion and Suggestions for Further Research

It's important to note that overvaluation during the IPO doesn't necessarily mean the company is not fundamentally strong or won't perform well in the long term. However, investors should be cautious and conduct thorough due diligence to assess whether the IPO price reflects the true value of the company or is inflated due to market dynamics and investor sentiment. Overvaluation can pose risks if the market corrects, and the stock price adjusts to align with the company's fundamentals.

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